

TARA	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LON DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	04	07	Concepcion	S 36	42.000	W 73	06.000
End	2021	05	09	Iquique	S 21	09.194	W 70	38.002

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

The objective of legs 3 and 4 was to make continuous measurements along surface water with the underway system (salinity, temperature, pH, pCO₂) and stations along and across the coastal line in the upwelling centers located in central and northern Chile.

This is imbibed on the general objective of the CEODOS program which is to evaluate the biological pump along the coast of Chile.

Particular emphasis was put on submarine canyons, in particular Nugurue, BioBlo and San Antonio canyon. The objective was to explore their ecological and biogeochemical role in the progression of oxygen deficient waters.

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Samuel Audrain
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves Tournon
3	CREW -	David Monmarché
4	CREW -	François Aurat
5	CREW -	Loïc Caudan
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie Bin
7	CREW - Media	Maeva Bardy/ Alice Roy
8	GUEST	Wilfried N'Sondé
9	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Josep Erta
10	SCIENCE - B - Chief Scientist	Camila Fernandez (Leg 3) / Emilio Alarcón (Leg 4)
11	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Eric Pelletier (leg 3) / Douglas Couet (leg 4)
12	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Douglas Couet (leg 3) / Eric Pelletier (leg 4)
13	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Milena Cerda
14	Observer from the SHOA	Josseline Fernández

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The focus of these legs was to sample three submarine canyons that actively export organic matter and follow the progression of the OMZ in northern and central Chile (Figure 1). We also related these features to the upwelling events influencing the coastal water off Concepcion, Valparaiso, Coquimbo and Iquique.

Indeed, the ecological role of submarine canyons will be tested in relation to the distribution of biological production offshore, seeing these features as OM export mechanisms.

A particular feature is the export of trace metals and heavy metals from the Atacama Desert to the ocean during Leg 4.

Figure1: 3D image of the extension of the OMZ in northern and central Chile (Ulloa and dePohl 2005).

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

We sampled 7 stations during leg 3 and 5 during leg 4. At each point we deployed the rosette+ctd to measure the physicochemical characteristics and to sample water in 6 depth for genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, nutrients, pH, TA, DOC, POC, pigments, etc., from the surface to 500 meters depth. The deepest casts were performed at 1200 m. Also, we deployed several nets with different mesh size (from 20 μm to 680 μm) in the surface and in the vertical water column to collect microorganisms.

Figure 2 shows a typical profile of Leg 3 in which we distinguish the signal equatorial subsurface waters with typical oxygen deficiency and a salinity maximum. Towards northern Chile, a secondary fluorescence maximum was often observed which probably corresponds to cyanobacteria and small size phytoplankton actively involved in carbon fixation. Among the main biological features expected for samples in leg 4, the capacity for potentially anoxygenic photosynthesis will be explored.

Figure 2: Cast CTD for Bio Bio canyon.

We deployed 3 argo floats destined to help filling the gap of physical data in northern and central Chile. This is a collaboration with CEAZA (UCN) and Mercator/Ifremer in France.

Concerning protocols, 2 tests stations for an alternative preservation method of samples for omics approaches were done successfully. At this occasion, we used dolphin rather than rosette for water surface sampling, with a significant gain of time for operation and processing. We chose to keep the use of the dolphin for the subsequent stations of leg 4.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide overview of sampling activities during the Campaign.

Table 1 Leg 3

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	CAST – Z00-Z10	CAST – Z00-D1	NET – WP11 20 - Horizontal	NET – WP11 20 - vertical	NET – WP11 200 - Horizontal	NET – WP11 200 - Vertical	CAST – Z00-D2	CAST – Z00+Z01+Z05	Bow Pole	Microtops	hTSRB	NET – Manta 330	CAST – Z01+Z03+Z05	NET – Régent 680	NET – Régent 680	Closing net 300 – 150 - 0m	Closing net 300 – 50 - 0m	CAST – Z07-Z09
021	20210411	36° 28.9	73°40.7	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
022	20210411	35° 34.1	73° 29.5																		
024	20210413	34°37.3	72° 21.9	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X	X
025	20210414	34°23.803	72° 38.50	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X	X
026	20210415	34°05.986	72° 50.86	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
027	20210417	33°31.977	71°46.5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X			X	X	X
028	20210418	33°22.081	72°13.146	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
029	20210419	33°06.783	72°25.0	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 2 Leg 4

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	CAST - Z00-Z10	CAST - Z00-D1 / Dolphin	NET - WP11 20 - Horizontal	NET - WP11 20 - vertical	NET - WP11 200 - Horizontal	NET - WP11 200 - Vertical	CAST - Z00-D2	CAST - Z00-Z01+Z05	Bow Pole	Microtops	hTSRB	NET - Manta 330	CAST - Z01+Z03+Z05	NET - Régent 680	NET - Régent 680	Closing net 300 - 150 - 0m	Closing net 300 - 50 - 0m	CAST - Z07-Z09
030	20210428	29°12.719	72°02.11	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
031	20210501	26°11.32	71° 35.16	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
032	20210505	22°03.56	71° 08.05	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
033	20210507	20°21.202	71° 19.32	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
034	20210508	20°14.905	70° 18.66	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Extra 1	20210430	27°13. 712	71°00.77		X		X		X								X				
Extra 2	20210506	21°09.194	70°38.802		X		X		X								X				

S320	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	164	0	0
S023	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	145	0	0
S<02	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E2000	250 mL	8											
E2000	500 mL	1											
F2000	250 mL	10											
pH	50 mL	60											
Salinity	300 mL	44											

TOTAL 309 159 242 153 0 175 0 245 19 474 590 219
3246